

Additional file 5: Self-reported complications at day 5

	Number of participants
Overall	17 / 34
- Hematoma	15
- Wound leakage	5
- Infection	0
- Bleeding	0
- Severe pain	3

Participants self-reported complications on the questionnaire and could choose multiple options.